

ECONOMICS OF HUMAN RESOURCES

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Annotation: Developmentally specific and appropriate the national mentality and values of our people of our Republic, which we have chosen and traditions, to a socially oriented market economy defining the way to build a transition, legal democratic state and civil society took The main priority is to deepen market reforms and the aim is to further liberalize the economy.

Keys word: “Workforce”, “human factor”, “human resources”, “labor potential”

Access - In most cases, the level of development of the society exists in the country determined by the number and composition of the population. The active part of the country's population is engaged in work, production, spends his energy, knowledge and skills to provide service. Active part of the population It consists of the population capable of working and able to work. Ability to work the duration of the period up to the specified level of human age, fitness for work and it means the level of mental and physical ability. And so, the active part of the population is called human resources Necessary physical and mental abilities depend on age, and youth and It forms and develops during adolescence, when it reaches the appropriate criteria fades and disappears. Historically, the working age limit has changed socially and economically came and averaged 30-50 years. Ability to work at the present time the lower limit in our republic is 16 years. This limit is 14-15 years in some countries, some are 18 years old. The upper limit of the ability to work is the majority 65 years for men (USA, Sweden) and women in both countries for 60 years (Germany, England, France). 0 in Uzbekistan this limit is 60

years for men and 55 years for women. To work the age limit of ability is also related to the average life expectancy.[1] The production of material goods and the provision of services are two essentials from the component: on the one hand, material resources (raw materials, equipment etc.) and on the other hand, from human resources, that is, professional skills and consists of employees with knowledge. In other words, the country human resources, which are a part of the population, along with material resources it also appears as a factor of economic development. However, these factors are different depending on their characteristics, they differ from each other with important signs. Today, it is a special feature of the training of qualified personnel consists of continuity. The socio-economic system of the Republic of Uzbekistan under conditions of independence and its own development, taking into account the characteristics of its traditions chose the model. Pre-reform personnel training and education system to the demands of democratic and market changes implemented in the republic did not answer. One of the main conditions for the country's development has improved consists in the functioning of the personnel training and education system. This system general and professional culture, social in a highly developed society and being personally active, making independent decisions in social and political life a new generation of people should be formed. 0 under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islorn Karimov The national model of the development of the state in terms of personnel training is National is the core of the program. The program is normative and scientific for reforms The foundation has been laid and is being introduced step by step since 1997. This document covers the nine-year general secondary education, in general, of a new, independent type — including secondary special, professional education, two-level higher education allows to fundamentally change the form and content of the educational system. Personnel the content and distinctive feature of the national training model is the integrity of the system, as its main constituents are the

following components: individual, state and society consists of including continuous education, science and production. Training and reforming the education system involves a long period of time — from defining the strategic directions of reforms to their completion takes the period of time, and it is with the manifestation of a number of laws It happens that knowing them allows you to manage this process. Currently, there is a crisis of labor activity and this crisis is the basis moving away from work, organizing the content of work in most workers lies in the loss of the concept of the task of achievement. That's why it's different entrepreneurship in forms is not only a means of livelihood, but also a person self-expression is also taking a big place as a solia. As a result a special type of social protection is formed in which a person overcomes the crisis to pass, to show oneself as a person in life by acquiring a new profession to occupy a new position and, at the same time, to a new field of activity will have a new social status due to his entry. Considering the problem of entrepreneurial employment from a socio-economic point of view provides a complex solution. In this case, a person is only a clear case not provided with a place, but his attitude to work changes, active creative work takes the place of passiveness. It is entrepreneurship allows to increase human initiative, improves him as a person. The economic situation in the country and the attitude of people to work without being changed, it cannot be fundamentally changed through various decisions or orders. This is a long evolutionary process, therefore the development of personality based on the necessity, to employees their interests, personal descriptions a comprehensive approach should be taken into account[2]

The main part- The concept of "labor potential" has been present since the 70-80s of the 20th century has been in force until today. It is the needs of a person in the field of work and arises as a subject of interests. As a factor of emergence, activation of personal factor opportunities and effective use of them comes from necessity. The concept of "human factor" dates back to the late 1980s and 1990s

has been in effect since. By the way, man is the main social production is the driving force. The concept of "human capital" has been around since the beginning of the 90s of the last century still in use. Human capital is formed as a result of investments It consists of a stock of knowledge, skills, abilities and reasons reflects physical, mental and psychological qualities and abilities of a person. Therefore, a person is the most effective object of realizing his knowledge It serves as a production through its own intellectual knowledge realizes its development. The concept of "human capital" has been around since the beginning of the 90s of the last century still in use. Human capital is formed as a result of investments It consists of a stock of knowledge, skills, abilities and reasons reflects physical, mental and psychological qualities and abilities of a person. Therefore, a person is the most effective object of realizing his knowledge It serves as a production through its own intellectual knowledge realizes its development. The concept of "human resources" appeared at the end of the 20th century. This large enterprises began to feel the need for personnel. Personnel training the act of planning and finding ways to use them effectively increased. Big funds to increase the ability of each employee began to be separated. The composition of the workforce and the requirements for it are increasing went High flexibility in workers, inclination to various benefits, professional preparation and desire to participate in computerized production it has been. Acceleration of scientific and technical progress is also a radical change in the economy made Man has become a controller and moderator of technological processes. Gaining new knowledge, improving professional skills, independent thinking, creative activity and initiative began to be required. Human resources are people. They only create material goods they also consume blessings. People have their material and They are not the same in terms of their spiritual needs. This includes their gender, age, health, family status, level of education and other social, psycho-physiological qualities cause. Therefore, one is not like the other (Figure 1.1 (62)). In the field of work, important needs of people are fulfilled,

but not all needs are fulfilled. Therefore, from human labor also keeping in mind his requirements as a person for effective use is important. In other words, this is the successful development of the economy requires that the operation of a complex economic mechanism is human determined by the quality level of resources. (21) Every citizen, every person is responsible for the development of society and its renewal it is necessary to determine his position and attitude. Realization of the goals set for the enterprise and organization from all the resources for - from the work of professors and expeditors, from laboratory equipment and metalworking machines, rolling stock from machine tools, oil and cotton raw materials, metal ore and water, money uses tools. How diverse are the resources used however, they are traditionally divided into three groups: natural or natural resources (land according to the definition of the French economist J.B. Eiting); material resources (capital) and human resources.[3] They can be called the factor of production. Human management is a component of management of any enterprise and organization part of it (along with material and natural resource management). However by definition, people are any resources used by organizations is different. Therefore, they require special management methods. First of all, people have intelligence (intellect, perception, intelligence), and their the reaction to the external environment (management) is not a mechanical one, but an emotional, conscious reaction. So, the organization and the employee are on the same page the interaction process is two-way. Secondly, people are constantly improving and developing are able. In the first period of his life, a person learns to walk, talk, read, learns to write and use a computer. When he comes to work will have professional skills. These skills are his entire career improves over time. In the current period of scientific and technical development the technologies used, and at the same time, professional skills are outdated left That is why my staff is constantly improving the ability to develop and the efficiency of the enterprise and organization is the most important and lasting source of growth. Thirdly, a person's

labor activity lasts 30-50 years in today's society is enough. Accordingly, mutual relations between people and enterprises and organizations also has a long duration. For example, in France, a person is average works for 16 years in one enterprise or organization. In Japan, until retirement will be hired until it is released. Fourth, unlike material and natural resources, Morocco has many people In some cases, the company and organization consciously set a specific goal they come and he works for this purpose they expect help from an enterprise or organization. The employee, as well as the enterprise and the satisfaction of the organization from working in mutual cooperation is an important condition for the continuation of cooperation. Every enterprise and organization in contact with human resources has its own regardless of the specific characteristics of its activity, it fulfills its purpose. How diverse are the enterprises and organizations in today's society in any case, the activities of each of them listed above will be available.[4]

Conclusion- Enterprises and organizations require highly productive labor. of labor its productivity should not decrease, but on the contrary, it should constantly increase. In the organization this situation is achieved mainly in three ways: a) selection of personnel; b) personnel replacement; c) personnel qualification improvement. A clear indicator of the quality of the workforce is the level of education and work release experience. Investing in human capital usually refers to skills, that is, any aimed at increasing labor productivity action is understood. According to the production and technical purpose, training of workers for the following allocated: 1) training of new workers; 2) retraining of workers and training for a second (interrelated) profession; 3) skill improvement. Personnel training, retraining and professional development – worker is an important link in balancing the supply and demand of power. Continuing education is a basic part of the national model of personnel training. He is an individual, a society that ensures the socio-economic development of the country and economic, social, scientific-

technical and cultural needs of the state. Satisfier is a priority area. At the same time, he is creative, socially active, spiritual formation of a rich personality and leading to highly qualified competitive personnel creates the necessary conditions for its preparation. A mechanism for managing the process of training qualified specialists — the quality of trained personnel and the level of their effective use influencing organizational, economic, legal, methodological relations, norms, is a collection of forms and methods. Retraining of personnel is a new profession for enterprise employees 0 is mastery. Training of personnel - acquiring their knowledge, skills and abilities as the result of production activity, such a special organized training to achieve the set goal in a short period of time allows.

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